

Psychological Diagnosis of Emotional Sphere Characteristics

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the analysis of methods and tools used for diagnosing the emotional sphere of personality. It discusses various approaches to assessing emotional states, their intensity, and the influence of emotions on behavior and mental health. Special attention is given to classical and modern diagnostic methods, such as emotional intelligence tests, questionnaires for assessing anxiety, depression, and stress, as well as projective methods. The article is intended for psychologists, psychotherapists, as well as students and researchers in the field of psychology.

Keywords: emotions, emotional regulation, emotional stability, sensitivity, emotional intelligence, affectivity, sensitivity, emotional perception, emotional lability, anxiety, depression, stress state, fear, reactivity, empathy, self-awareness, self-regulation.

Introduction

This article is dedicated to the analysis of methods and tools used for diagnosing the emotional sphere of personality. It discusses various approaches to assessing emotional states, their intensity, and the influence of emotions on behavior and mental health. The focus is on both classical and modern diagnostic methods, such as emotional intelligence tests, questionnaires for assessing anxiety, depression, and stress, as well as projective methods. The author emphasizes the importance of diagnosing the emotional sphere to identify disruptions in the psycho-emotional state and to develop effective methods for psychocorrection and psychotherapy with clients. This article is intended for psychologists, psychotherapists, as well as students and researchers in the field of psychology.

The emotional sphere of personality represents an essential component of a person's mental life, influencing their behavior, perception of the surrounding reality, and interaction with others. Emotions are fundamental for decision-making and play a key role in social interactions. Psychological diagnosis of the emotional sphere helps to identify the characteristics of emotional reactions, levels of emotional stability, and to determine potential psychological deviations and disorders.

1. Psychological Diagnostics: Basic Concepts and Methods

Psychological diagnostics is the process of identifying and assessing various aspects of a person's mental activity and state. In the context of the emotional sphere, diagnostic procedures are aimed at studying the nature, intensity, and direction of emotional experiences, as well as a person's ability to regulate their emotions in different life situations.

There are various methods of psychological diagnostics, including:

- **Tests and questionnaires.** These are standard techniques for assessing emotions, such as mood scales, tests for evaluating levels of anxiety and depression.
- **Observation.** Emotional reactions can be assessed by observing a person's behavior in various situations.
- **Interviews and conversations.** Personal characteristics and emotional states can also be identified through one-on-one conversations with a therapist or psychologist.
- **Psychophysiological methods.** For example, measuring heart rate or skin galvanic response can be used to diagnose emotional states.

At present, the psychology of emotions significantly lags behind other areas of general psychology, such as the psychology of memory, thinking, attention, sensation, etc., in terms of theoretical development. The psychology of emotions lacks a unified theory of emotions, and the issue of classifying emotional phenomena has not been resolved. As researchers admit, the arts, especially literature and painting, have advanced much further and deeper in the study of the emotional sphere than science.

"The lack of interest" among scientists in this issue is attributed by some authors to the fact that emotional phenomena, in themselves, do not fit within the framework of the positivist approach, which dominates modern science and is oriented toward the principles of materialism and objectivism in scientific research. Emotions and feelings are perhaps the most subjective mental formations, with the main characteristics being their diversity and dynamism. All of this significantly complicates the implementation of a scientific approach to the study of the emotional sphere of personality. At the same time, the importance of the problem of scientific analysis of emotions hardly requires justification. Every moment of a person's existence is accompanied by a certain mental state, which is, in one way or another, emotionally colored. Thus, P.M. Jakobson emphasizes that in their feelings and experiences, a person as a personality is expressed much more vividly than in intellectual activity.

Overview of Methods for Studying Certain Aspects of the Emotional Sphere

The review of methods that allow the investigation of various aspects of the emotional sphere also points to the underdevelopment of this issue. Among the specific methods, it is first necessary to note the quite large number of questionnaires aimed at identifying the degree of expression of certain psychodynamic traits of personality related to the emotional sphere (emotional lability in temperament questionnaires, anxiety level, aggressiveness, emotional sensitivity in personality questionnaires, etc.). One of the drawbacks of existing survey methods is that they do not allow studying the entire diversity of the emotional sphere of the personality. As for projective methods that investigate the emotional sphere of a specific individual in one way or another, their application also leads to the reduction of the diversity of emotional experiences to several key concepts, often of a clinical nature (conflict, frustration, guilt, etc.). The general conclusion regarding methods of studying the emotional sphere is as follows: at present, there is a need for the development of specialized methods that allow us to investigate both the diversity of emotions and feelings, as well as the specificity of each emotional experience of an individual.

The psychophysical approach, in general, and a number of psychophysical studies, in particular, seem highly productive as a methodological basis for solving the task at hand. First of all, they can encompass the entire diversity of emotions through the concept of "emotional space" (by analogy with the concept of "sensory space" introduced by O.M. Zabrodin for studying the diversity of sensory sensations). Secondly, the theory of scales and subjective planning may, in our opinion, serve as the starting point in studying the numerous experiences of a person, their various modalities, and intensities. It is known that S. Stevens stated that the problem of stimulus evaluation is the fundamental problem not only of psychophysics but also of psychology in general, since there is no mental

phenomenon to which subjective evaluation does not relate. Emotions and feelings are also mental phenomena, and thus the individual also produces some evaluation of them, from which it can be concluded that these mental phenomena form a certain ordered structure that can be designated as the emotional space of the personality.

Research by domestic psychophysicists (A.A. Ponukalin, T.D. Kalistratova) has shown that the essence of subjective evaluation manifests itself in verbal form, and therefore, the evaluation of verbal stimuli characterizing an emotional state seems to be the most adequate form for reflecting the structure of the emotional space of an individual.

It should be noted that modern psychological diagnostics is becoming increasingly oriented toward the subjective paradigm of data analysis (A.G. Shmelev, N.N. Koroleva), according to which the subject is characterized by numerous parameters in multidimensional space. This approach allows for penetrating into the inner world of the personality and reconstructing its individuality.

Summarizing all of the above, we formulate the requirements for methods of studying the emotional space of a personality:

1. The stimulus material of these methods should contain verbal stimuli—concepts denoting emotions and feelings.
2. The results of the examination should reconstruct the holistic system of an individual's representations of the components of their emotional experiences, which will help recognize problem areas, restructure, and regulate one's understanding of the sphere of emotions and feelings.
3. The work of the subject with the stimulus material should be based on the principle of subjective calibration and the evaluation of specific emotional experiences and their diversity.

Diagnostic Methods Various methods are used to diagnose emotional characteristics. Here are some of them:

1. **Projective Methods**

Projective methods, such as the Rorschach test or the TAT (Thematic Apperception Test), help to explore hidden aspects of personality and the emotional sphere of an individual. These methods are based on the analysis of responses to ambiguous stimuli, which helps to identify unconscious emotions and conflicts.

2. **Questionnaires and Surveys**

Standardized questionnaires and surveys are used to diagnose emotional states, such as:

- **Beck Depression Inventory** – determines the level of depression.
- **Spielberger Anxiety Inventory** – measures the level of anxiety in an individual.
- **Eysenck Personality Inventory** – aimed at diagnosing emotional reactivity and stability.

3. **Self-Assessment and Self-Reports**

Self-reports can be useful for understanding how a person perceives their emotions, how often they experience certain feelings, and how these feelings affect their behavior.

4. **Behavioral Observations**

In some cases, methods of observing a person's behavior in various situations are used to diagnose the emotional sphere. For example, analyzing how a person reacts to stress, conflicts, or joyful events allows us to assess their emotional stability.

5. **Psychophysiological Methods** These methods involve measuring physiological reactions (such as heart rate, skin galvanic response) when exposed to emotional stimuli, which helps assess the degree of emotional tension and the body's reactions to emotions.

Emotional Regulation One of the key aspects of diagnosing the emotional sphere is the study of a person's ability to regulate their emotions. Emotional regulation includes:

- **Awareness of one's emotions:** the ability to recognize and name one's emotions.
- **Emotion management:** the ability to control the intensity of emotions and cope with them in different situations.
- **Maintaining emotional balance:** the ability to keep one's emotional state without letting emotions dominate behavior and problem-solving.

Inability to regulate emotions can lead to the development of various psychopathological conditions, such as depression, anxiety, aggression, and others.

Emotional Disorders Some individuals may have difficulty regulating their emotions, leading to emotional disorders. The most common disorders include:

- **Anxiety disorders:** characterized by excessive worry and anxiety.
- **Depression:** an emotional disorder marked by prolonged sadness, loss of interest, and reduced activity.
- **Borderline Personality Disorder:** emotional regulation disorders associated with extreme mood changes and impulsive actions.
- **Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD):** emotional disturbance resulting from trauma.

Given these requirements, we developed a method for studying the emotional space of a personality (MEPS). The stimulus material includes 183 concepts reflecting the diversity of emotional experiences captured in the Russian language. The creation of this list involved several stages: initially, all concepts characterized as "state, emotion, feeling, experience, attitude" were extracted from the "Dictionary of the Modern Russian Language" by Ozhegov. More than 400 terms were identified. Then, based on further work with the literature, situation-related characteristics (enmity, conflict), personality traits (anxiety, pride), and expressions describing emotions rather than the emotions themselves (crying, laughter) were excluded. As a result, a list was formed that represents the diversity of personal experiences and can serve as a basis for studying the holistic structure of these experiences.

The analysis of the results of the examination implies comparison with classifications related to a differentiated approach to emotions (with a limited number of basic experiences highlighted). It is also planned to compare the obtained data with classifications of emotions that attempt to describe the emotional sphere multidimensionally based on factor analysis data, identifying leading axes containing polar characteristics of emotions. When studying age-related characteristics of the emotional sphere (which is the primary goal of our research), it is proposed to compare data from different age groups of subjects and identify both quantitative and qualitative differences that characterize the emotional sphere of the individuals examined. Quantitative indicators include: the number of most frequent and least frequent experiences, and the number of groups of experiences distinguished by the subject. Qualitative indicators include: modality and intensity of the most frequent and least frequent experiences, homogeneity of emotions within each group, and the key concept around which each group of experiences is formed. The analysis of these parameters allows for a comprehensive description of the emotional space, its complexity, and differentiation in subjects of various age groups.

Emphasizing the significance of studying various aspects of the psychology of emotions, V.K. Vilonas writes: "Affectivity, as the most intimate and specific characteristic of the mental, may even surpass the importance of the intellectual component. Without solving the problem of emotions, the development of a general theory of the mind is impossible."

Conclusion The emotional sphere of a person can be subject to various disorders, both in the case of impaired emotional regulation and in the case of a deficit or excess of certain emotions. For example, excessive anxiety or depression can significantly reduce a person's quality of life and also affect their physical health. It is important to note that emotional disorders are often accompanied by disruptions in cognitive processes and social interactions.

Psychological diagnostics of the emotional sphere is a key tool for identifying emotional characteristics and their impact on daily life. Early diagnosis allows timely identification of problems in the emotional sphere and the development of effective strategies for their correction and treatment. Individual characteristics of perception and expression of emotions require a comprehensive approach to diagnostics and subsequent therapy.

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